

TABLE 1

Sr. No.	R	M.P.	Mol. formula	Analysis %					
				C	Calc. H	N	Found C	Found H	Found N
1	2-OH	75	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₅ O	74.23	5.84	14.43	74.08	5.81	14.14
2	4-OH	210	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₅ O	74.23	5.84	14.43	74.14	5.76	14.21
3	4-OCH ₃	124	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₅ O	74.74	6.23	13.77	74.58	6.26	13.56
4	4-N ₂ O	155	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂	67.51	5.00	17.50	67.46	4.93	17.33

ssium cyanide (0.01 mole) in 10 ml water was added to the imine solution with continuous stirring at 0-5°. The precipitate (II) obtained was filtered and recrystallised from methanol. Other nitriles were prepared in an analogous way. Yield 70-80%.

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TABLE 2

S. No.	R	M.P. °C	Mol. formula	Analysis %	
				Calc. N	Found
5	2-OH	133	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₄ O	17.61	17.42
6	4-OH	220	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O	17.61	17.65
7	4-OCH ₃	162	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ O	16.90	16.71
8	4-NO ₂	145	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₂	20.17	20.09

Reduction of imines with NaBH₄ (Table-3): Sodium borohydride (0.03 mole) was added to a methanolic solution of the imine (0.02 mole) over a period of ½ hour at 5-10°. After which the reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The excess of sodium borohydride was destroyed by the addition of water and the product was obtained by extraction with ether. The ether extract was washed with water until neutral, dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate and evaporated. The compound (III) thus obtained was recrystallised from methanol. Other dihydrocompounds were obtained in a similar manner. Yield 55-62%.

TABLE 3

S. No.	R	M.P.	Mol. formula	Analysis %	
				Calc. N	Found
9	2-OH	140	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₅ O	14.34	14.19
10	4-OH	156	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₅ O	14.34	14.14
11	4-OCH ₃	110	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₅ O	13.67	13.56
12	4-NO ₂	113	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	17.39	17.31

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Chemical Constituents of *Aconitum violacium* and *Polygonum tomentosum*

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ACONITUM (N. O. Ranunculaceae) is a large genera widely distributed throughout the Northern temperate regions. These are highly poisonous and most valuable medicinal plants¹. The literature survey of the genus *Aconitum* has revealed it to be a rich source of alkaloids²⁻⁶.

The air dried powdered roots (1 kg) were defatted with petroleum ether and then exhaustively extracted with ethanol. The ethanolic extract was concentrated to viscous mass, dissolved in acidulated water (1% HCl), the resulting solution basified with sodium carbonate and then extracted with chloroform. The aqueous solution left after the extraction with chloroform gave positive Molisch's test for the presence of sugars which were identified as glucose and rhamnose by co-chromatographic studies with authentic samples.

The chloroform extract on concentration gave a colourless solid mass which was purified by dissolving it in methanol and reprecipitating with water. The

white mass so obtained was recrystallised from ethanol as white crystals, $C_{36}H_{51}O_{11}$ (m/e 673), m.p. 112-14°, acetyl derivative, m.p. 196-98°. It was characterized as bikhaconitine by co-tlc; m.m.p. and superimposable I.R.⁷ with the authentic sample.

Polygonum is a large genera, cosmopolitan but distributed especially throughout the temperate regions. The drug finds extensive uses in medicine⁸. The literature survey of the genus *Polygonum* shows that it is a rich source of flavonoids⁹⁻¹³.

The air dried powdered plant (4 kg) was extracted with hot ethanol. The ethanolic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and the thick viscous mass so obtained was refluxed for several times with petroleum ether to remove chlorophyll and fats. The residual mass was extracted with acetone. The acetone extract after concentration under reduced pressure was extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was concentrated and then chromatographed over a column of magnesol¹⁴. On eluting with ethyl-acetate saturated with water two compounds, A and B, were obtained.

Compound A crystallised from a mixture of acetone: methanol (1:1) as light yellow crystals, $C_{15}H_{16}O_7$ (m/e 302), m.p. 316°, formed an acetate, $C_{25}H_{26}O_{12}$, m.p. 198-99°, O-CH₃ derivative $C_{26}H_{28}O_7$ (m/e 372), m.p. 145-46°. It was characterised as quercetin by comparison of m.p. and I.R.¹⁵ with those of authentic sample of quercetin.

Compound B crystallised from methanol as yellow crystals, $C_{16}H_{12}O_7$ (m/e 316), m.p. 294-96°(d.), formed an acetate, m.p. 184-86°, co-tlc, m.m.p. and superimposable IR¹⁵ confirmed its identity with authentic rhamnetin.

The residual acetone extract (left after extraction with ether) was chromatographed over a magnesol column and eluted with ethyl acetate saturated with water, when two flavonoids, C and D were obtained.

Flavonoid C crystallised from methanol as yellow crystals, $C_{21}H_{20}O_{11}$, m.p. 185-87°, gave positive Molisch's test indicating it to be a glycoside. The compound on hydrolysis with 7% sulphuric acid gave quercetin and rhamnose. Co-chromatographic examination and m.m.p. with authentic sample showed it to be quercitrin.

Flavonoid D crystallised from methanol as yellow crystals, $C_{27}H_{30}O_{16}$, m.p. 210-12°. On hydrolysis with 7% sulphuric acid it gave quercetin, glucose and rhamnose and on partial hydrolysis with formic acid¹⁶, quercetin-3-*o*- β -glucoside and rhamnose were obtained. Its identity with rutin was established by m.m.p. with the authentic sample.

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3-Arylisocoumarin : Synthesis of 3-(2',4'-Dihydroxyphenyl)- ; 3-(2'-methyl-, 4'-hydroxyphenyl)- ; and 3-(3'-methyl-, 4'-hydroxyphenyl)-isocoumarins.

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IN continuation of our previous work¹, we report here the condensation of resorcinol, *m*-cresol and *o*-cresol with homophthalic anhydride or acid (I) in the presence of polyphosphoric acid which furnished the corresponding 3-phenylisocoumarin derivatives(II) in 50% yields. These isocoumarin derivatives were subjected to different reactions, e.g. alkaline hydrolysis